

Cerdà-Navarro, A., Salvà-Mut, F. ; Adame-Obrador, T. & Sureda-García, I. (2019). Tackling intermediate vocational education and training dropout: Contributions from the student engagement perspective. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.278-283) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641060>

Tackling intermediate vocational education and training dropout: Contributions from the student engagement perspective

Cerdà-Navarro, Antoni

University of Balearic Islands (Spain)/ Department of Applied Pedagogy and Educational Psychology, antoni.cerda@uib.cat

Salvà-Mut , Francesca

University of Balearic Islands (Spain)/ Department of Applied Pedagogy and Educational Psychology, f.salva@uib.es

Adame-Obrador , Teresa

University of Balearic Islands (Spain)/ Department of Applied Pedagogy and Educational Psychology, teresa.adame@uib.es

Sureda-García, Inmaculada

University of Balearic Islands (Spain)/ Department of Applied Pedagogy and Educational Psychology, inmaculada.sureda@uib.es

1 Introduction & background

Spain combines high rates of Early Leaving from Education and Training (ELET) with low rates of participation in Vocational Education and Training (VET). In 2016 the Spanish ELET rate was of 19.0%, while the rate was 10.7% for the EU (Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport, 2017). Recent studies place the percentage of students enrolled in VET on the total number of students enrolled in upper secondary education between 33.5% and 35% (CedefopReferNet Spain, 2015, 2017, OECD), while for the whole of the EU (EU-26) the percentage is of 48.5% and the average of the OECD is 46% (OECD, 2017). The qualification rate is also higher in Advanced Secondary Education (*bachillerato*) (69.8%) than in Intermediate VET (IVET) (50.5%) (Authors, 2017a).

The Balearic Islands, the Autonomous Community where the research presented is placed, registers even higher ELET rates than the rest of Spain (26.8%) (Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport, 2017), as well as a lower average participation rate and a slightly higher percentage of completion of IVET studies (Authors, 2017a).

In this context, and in accordance with recent reports on the subject (Cedefop, 2016) tackling IVET dropout is a central issue to contribute to the decrease of ELET. We also want to highlight their contribution to the exercise of an active citizenship and of more inclusive and sustainable societies.

The text we present is part of the project “Pathways leading to success in, or dropout from, vocational training in the education system at levels 1 and 2” (“Itinerarios de éxito y abandono en la formación profesional del Sistema educativo en nivel 1 y 2” – Ref – EDU2013-42854-R), (www.itinerariosfp.org), funded by the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness, the Spanish National Research Agency (AEI) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).

The concept of student engagement, one of the most commonly used in research on secondary education dropout, is one of the central theoretical references of our research. According to Reschly & Christenson (2012) it is a metaconstruct that brings together different

research approaches developed from different disciplines and includes three types of engagement: behavioural engagement (participation in academic activities, social or extracurricular), emotional engagement (positive or negative affect on interactions with teachers, peers, academic activities, school), cognitive engagement (personal performance of cognitive or intellectual capital, self-regulation and effort to acquire a good level of knowledge). It is also characterized by the influence of the environment (family, school, community...) and for providing elements for intervention as evidenced in the model of association between context, commitment and results of students based on the project Check & Connect (Reschly & Christenson, 2012). These features are coherent with the objectives of the research and the results of previous research projects on the subject in the context of the Balearic Islands (Authors, 2014; Authors, 2015).

The questions we want to answer in this text are the following: *In which dimensions and variables of student engagement are there significant differences between students continuing their studies in second year and students who leave during the first year or at the end of it? How can this knowledge contribute to the prevention of IVET dropout?*

2 Methodology

Participants

The field work is done in the Balearic Islands (Spain) and the sample (statistically representative) is constituted by 1091 students who started IVET during 2015-16. Of these, at the beginning of the year 2016-17, 844 (77,4%) continued studying the same course, while 231 (21.2%) had left it and 16 (1,5%) is collected as missing data.

Procedure

Student engagement data was collected through a paper self-questionnaire in 70 classrooms of the 21 centres that participated in the study, after approval of the Ethics Committee of the University of the Balearic Islands (UIB). Information about perseverance and dropout has been reported by centres.

Student engagement factors

4 student engagement factors based on 28 items were used in the analysis. Each one of these items was to be responded to on a scale of agreement or disagreement, where 0="Totally disagree," 1="Disagree," 2="Agree," and 3="Totally agree." The factors used are: a) Relationship with teachers (9 items) ($\alpha=,82$); b) Relationships with peers (5 items) ($\alpha=,78$); c) Misbehavior at school (4 items) ($\alpha=,58$); d) School Effort (10 items) ($\alpha=,79$).

Data Analysis

Firstly, we calculated average scores in each of the 4 factors of student engagement. Then, t-tests were carried out to independent samples with the aim of finding statistically significant differences between the two groups (dropout/continue) under study. Finally, in order to determine the size of the effect of these differences, Cohen D was calculated.

3 Results

The results (see table 1) show that the differences between one and another group are significant in the global dimension of the relationships with teachers, as well as in each and every one of the variables that compose it. Conversely, in the global relations between peers, there are no significant differences, as in any of its variables. In the section on indiscipline, the only significant difference lies in the fact that those who leave school present a higher rate of absenteeism. In the dimension of school effort, significant differences are observed in most of the variables.

Table 1 Student engagement and dropout

	Dropout (between 1rst. and 2nd. academic year)			D C OHE N
	Non- dropout	Dro pout	To tal (A vg.)	
P1.a My teachers are available when I need them.	2,22a	2,05 b	2, 16	0, 26
P1.b The teaching staff at my school listens to students.	2,18a	1,95 b	2, 10	0, 38
P1.c The rules at the school where I study are fair.	1,98a	1,85 b	1, 94	0, 17
P1.d The teaching staff at my school is interested in me as a person, not just as a student.	1,79a	1,53 b	1, 70	0, 33
P1.e In general, my teachers are open and honest with me.	2,21a	1,99 b	2, 14	0, 32
P1.f In general, the teaching staff at my school treats students appropriately.	2,21a	2,03 b	2, 15	0, 28
P1.g I like talking with the teachers at my school.	2,03a	1,76 b	1, 94	0, 38
P1.h I feel safe at my school.	2,22a	2,06 b	2, 17	0, 24
P1.i At my school, most teachers care about students.	2,01a	1,82 b	1, 95	0, 26
Relationships with the teaching staff	2,09a	1,90 b	2, 03	0, 44
n	739	352	10 91	
P2.a My peers care about me.	2,05a	1,95 a	2, 02	0, 15
P2.b My peers help me when I need their help.	2,25a	2,26 a	2, 25	- 0,02
P2.c My peers respect my opinions.	2,08a	2,04 a	2, 07	0, 07
P2.d I like communicating with my peers.	2,42a	2,43 a	2, 43	- 0,02
P2.e I have friends at my school.	2,46a	2,39 a	2, 44	0, 11
Relationships with peers	2,25a	2,21 a	2, 24	0, 09
n	739	352	10 91	
P5.a I am purposely a bother in class.	,23a	,33a	0, 26	- 0,16
P5.b I respond to the teacher in a manner that is inappropriate	,24a	,34a	0, 27	- 0,14
P5.c I use "cheat sheets" or other methods for copying during exams.	,27a	,38a	0, 31	- 0,16

P5.d I have missed class(es) without an excuse.	,63a	,98b	0,75	-0,37
School misbehavior	,34a	,50b	0,39	-0,32
n	739	352	1091	
P7.a Before turning in school work or homework, I go over it to ensure that I did it correctly.	2,26a	2,18a	2,24	0,12
P7.b When I do a school activity, I try to have a good understanding of what I am doing.	2,43a	2,29b	2,38	0,24
P7.c When I try hard in studies, the results I get are positive	2,31a	2,11b	2,25	0,28
P7.d I believe that exams, tests or class exercises are a good tool to know what I have learned.	2,07a	2,04a	2,06	0,04
P7.e What I am learning in my classes is important for my future career.	2,53a	2,45a	2,50	0,12
P7.f I compare myself with my classmates to know if I'm learning at the right pace	1,73a	1,73a	1,73	0,00
P7.g Studying will offer me many career opportunities in the future.	2,53a	2,40b	2,49	0,21
P7.h I wish to continue my education once I finish with my current study program.	2,36a	2,19b	2,30	0,22
P7.i The studies that I am taking make me optimistic about my professional future.	2,33a	2,14b	2,27	0,27
P7.j I like the profession for which I am receiving training.	2,44a	2,18b	2,35	0,34
School effort	2,30a	2,17b	2,26	0,29
n	739	352	1091	

Note: the values of the same row and subtable that do not share the same subscript are significantly different at $p < 0.01$ in the bilateral equality test for column means. Boxes without a subscript are not included in the test. The tests assume equal variances.

4 Conclusions

These results may contribute to the prevention of IVET dropout, as they illustrate the differences and similarities between students that leave school and students who persevere in them, in relation to some of the main dimensions of student engagement. The results show the central role of the relations with teachers in the differentiation between the student group that leaves and the student group that continues, as well as how significant the differences in some other items closely related to educational practices are. They are coherent with the results

obtained in the review of the literature on the subject (Autors, 2017b) as well as in specific case studies carried out in the framework of the same project (Autors, 2017c).

References

- CEDEFOP (2016). *Leaving education early: putting vocational education and training centre stage. Volume I: investigating causes and extent*. Publications Office. Cedefop research paper No 57, Luxembourg, Belgium.
- Cedefop ReferNet Spain (2015). *Spotlight on VET SPAIN 2015*. Retrieved from <http://www.cedefop.europa.eu/es/publications-and-resources/publications/8104>.
- Cerdà-Navarro, A.; Sureda-Negre, J. & Comas-Forgas, R. (2017) Recommendations for confronting vocational education dropout: a literature review. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training* 9:17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-017-0061-4>
- Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte (2017). *Sistema estatal de indicadores de la educación 2017*. Retrieved from: <https://www.mecd.gob.es/inee/indicadores/sistema-estatal/edicion-2017.html>
- OECD (2017). *Education at a Glance 2017: OECD Indicators*. Paris: OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/eag-2017-en>.
- Pinya Medina, C., Pomar Fiol, M. I. & Salvà Mut, F. (2017). Prevenir el abandono educativo en la educación secundaria profesional: aportaciones del alumnado y del profesorado. *Profesorado. Revista de currículum y formación del profesorado*, 21 (4), 95-117.
- Reschly, A.L. & Christenson, S.L. (2012). Jingle, Jangle, and Conceptual Haziness: Evolution and Future Directions of the Engagement Construct. En Christenson, S.L.; Reschly, A. & Wylie, C. (ed.). *Handbook of Research on Student Engagement*. NY: Springer. P. 3-20. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-2018-7_1
- Salvà-Mut, F. (2017). Formación profesional de grado medio y abandono temprano de la educación y la formación en España: una aproximación territorial. Paper presented at the *International Workshop Preventing educational dropout in secondary VET*, Palma de Mallorca, 18 and 19 December 2017.
- Salvà-Mut, F., Oliver-Trobat, M.F. & Comas-Forgas, R. (2014). Abandono escolar y desvinculación de la escuela: perspectiva del alumnado. *magis, Revista Internacional de Investigación en Educación*, 6 (13), 129-142.
- Salvà-Mut, F.; Quintana-Murci, E. & Desmarais, D. (2015). Inclusion and exclusion factors in adult education of youth with a low educational level in Spain. *European Journal of Research on the Education and Learning of Adults*, 6 (1), 9-23.

Biographical notes

Antoni Cerdà-Navarro. FPI predoc researcher.sociology degree, master's degree in sociology and public policies for the university of valencia and master's degree in applied social research and data analysis for "sociological research center" (cis). he has several experiences as a researcher in the department of sociology and social anthropology at the university of valencia; in the department of international assessments of the national institute of educational evaluation (inee). at the present time he has a fpi predoc contract as a researcher in university of balearic islands.

Francesca Salvà-Mut. Associate professor. phd in educational sciences and associate professor since 1996 in the department of applied pedagogy and educational psychology at the balearic islands university (uib). she has been visiting researcher at several international centres, among which are: université laval (quebec, canada), université du québec à montreal (quebec, canada), centre for the study of education and work, ontario institute for studies in education of the university of toronto (toronto, canada). research areas: school dropout;

training and career paths; young people with low education profiles; gender, work and education.

Teresa Adame-Obrador. Associate professor. graduate in psychology (1989) and doctor in psychopedagogics (2000) for the balearic islands university. professor since 1990 in the department of applied pedagogy and educational psychology at the balearic islands university (uib). research areas: training and career paths; school dropout; young people with low education profiles; educational guidance.

Inmaculada Sureda-García. Associate professor. phd. at the department of applied education and educational psychology of the university of the balearic islands (uib). holds a phd. in psychology and pedagogy, and is member of the research group 'education and citizenship'. his main areas of interest are: social and emotional competencies, peer rejection.